

Біліченко Валерій Віталійович
Старший викладач кафедри
тактико- спеціальної підготовки,
Дніпровський державний
університет внутрішніх справ
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17340129>

РОЛЬ ТАКТИКО- СПЕЦІАЛЬНОЇ ПІДГОТОВКИ У ФОРМУВАННІ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ КОМПЕ- ТЕНТНОСТІ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ПРАВООХОРОННИХ ОРГАНІВ

Bilichenko Valeriy Vitaliyovych
Senior Lecturer, Department of
Tactical and Special Training,
Dnipro State
University of Internal Affairs

THE ROLE OF TACTICAL AND SPECIAL TRAINING IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICERS

Анотація.

Метою роботи є комплексний аналіз ролі тактико-спеціальної підготовки у формуванні професійної компетентності правоохоронців. Актуальність дослідження зумовлена необхідністю розгляду цієї підготовки як цілісного соціально-професійного феномену, що поєднує практичні навички, психологічну готовність і тактичну грамотність. Методологічну основу становлять системно-структурний підхід, метод порівняльного аналізу, узагальнення наукових положень і практичного досвіду Національної поліції. Результати дослідження підтвердили, що тактико-спеціальна підготовка є визначальним чинником професійної компетентності та ефективності діяльності правоохоронних органів. Перспективи подальших наукових досліджень полягають у вивченні інноваційних методик і технологій підготовки та їх адаптації до сучасних безпекових викликів.

Abstract.

The purpose of the work is a comprehensive analysis of the role of tactical and special training in the formation of professional competence of law enforcement officers. The relevance of the study is due to the need to consider this training as a holistic socio-professional phenomenon that combines practical skills, psychological readiness and tactical literacy. The methodological basis will be a system-structural approach, a method of comparative analysis, a generalization of scientific provisions and practical experience of the National Police. The results of the study confirmed that tactical and special training is a determining factor in the professional competence and effectiveness of law enforcement agencies. Prospects for further scientific research lie in studying innovative training methods and technologies and their adaptation to modern security challenges.

Ключові слова: тактико- спеціальна підготовка, професійна компетентність, службова діяльність, стратегічне мислення, ефективність правоохоронної діяльності.

Keywords: tactical and special training, professional competence, service activities, strategic thinking, effectiveness of law enforcement activities.

Tactical and special training is an organized, almost continuous process of acquiring knowledge, special skills and abilities necessary for the effective performance of official duties [1, p. 612]. It occupies a key place in the system of professional education and official activity of law enforcement officers, as it ensures the practical readiness of personnel to perform tasks in conditions that are as close as possible to real ones. Its significance goes beyond exclusively physical or technical training, because it forms a complex combination of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and psychological stability, which is the foundation of the professional competence of a law enforcement officer.

According to O. Didenko, competence, as a complex personal category, means a person's practical readiness and ability to act in a certain field; it encompasses theoretical knowledge, ideas, skills, motives, values, and assumes the presence of practical experience [2, p.

71]. In this context, competence should be understood not only as a set of individual professional characteristics, but as an integral quality that is formed in the process of continuous training and practical application of acquired knowledge and skills. It acquires particular importance in the field of law enforcement, where the level of professional training determines the effectiveness of performing official tasks, ensuring public safety, and protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens. Tactical and special training in this case appears as a key component that not only ensures the formation of relevant professional skills, but also contributes to the development of stress resistance, the ability to quickly navigate in dynamic conditions and make optimal decisions.

The concept of professional competence is key in the scientific literature when characterizing the level of

professionalism of a specialist. The modern modernization of the law enforcement system of Ukraine is aimed at ensuring that the results of its functioning correspond to public demands and expectations of citizens. This determines the objective need to improve the system of professional training of police officers, which involves the formation and development of communicative, psychological, conflictological and special professional competencies in them. It is their purposeful mastery that is considered an urgent task, the solution of which directly affects the quality of law enforcement activities. [3, pp. 266-267].

Given the complexity and multifaceted nature of modern challenges in the context of complex socio-political and economic transformations taking place in Ukraine, the role of the National Police as a key institution for ensuring law and order, public safety and protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens is growing, therefore such training becomes an important factor in forming the ability of law enforcement officers to act effectively in extreme and non-standard situations, make timely decisions and bear personal responsibility for their consequences. [4, p. 212]. It contributes not only to the development of algorithms for actions in specific operational circumstances, but also to the development of the ability to flexibly adapt to the changing conditions of modernity.

The formation of professional competence of law enforcement officers in modern conditions is considered as a multidimensional and dynamic process, encompassing systemic transformations of the personality, aimed at the development of both practical and ideological and motivational characteristics. Tactical and special training is an important factor that ensures the integrity and interconnection of key subsystems of the professional development of a law enforcement officer. In particular, we are talking about:

- subsystem of professionalism of activity, which includes the improvement of professional competence, the formation and consolidation of practical skills and abilities;

- subsystem of professionalism of personality, which includes the development of intellectual abilities, professionally significant and business qualities, the formation of a reflective culture, the formation of creative and innovative potential, as well as motivational attitudes towards achievement;

- subsystem of normativity of activity and behavior, which involves the construction of a moral and legal system for the regulation of professional behavior, activity and relationships;

- a subsystem of a productive self-concept, which ensures a harmonious combination of personal and professional development [5, p. 240].

In the context of the above subsystems, tactical and special training performs an integrative function, as it is aimed at forming the readiness of law enforcement officers to act in extreme and unpredictable conditions, while maintaining the ability to make effective decisions and timely assess the situation. An important component of such training is the development of tactical literacy, which includes the ability to assess the situation, determine acceptable solutions in conditions

of uncertainty and risk, plan and implement operational measures, as well as effectively communicate and coordinate the actions of colleagues [6, p. 183].

Tactical literacy occupies a leading place in the structure of professional competence of law enforcement officers, as it ensures their ability to effectively perform official tasks in various operational conditions. Tactics are understood as a systematized set of methods and techniques used to achieve the set goal. In this context, tactical and special training of police officers is a continuous educational and practical process aimed at deepening professional knowledge, developing skills and abilities necessary for developing an optimal model of behavior and choosing adequate methods of action in complex and non-standard situations of official activity [7, p. 85].

Tactical literacy appears not only as a set of practical skills, but also as an important intellectual and analytical resource that ensures the optimal use of available forces and means in a specific operational situation. It encompasses the ability of a law enforcement officer to foresee possible scenarios of events, minimize risks and avoid tactical errors that can have critical consequences for the performance of official tasks. In view of this, tactical literacy is a key element of professional competence, as it combines theoretical knowledge with practical skills for their application in dynamic conditions of official activity [8, p. 586].

Thus, tactical and special training is a key component of the formation of professional competence of law enforcement officers, as it provides a comprehensive combination of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and psychological stability, which is the foundation of professional skill. It performs an integrative function, combining subsystems of professionalism of activity, personal development, normativity of behavior and productive self-concept, and thereby ensures the readiness of police officers to act effectively in extreme, unpredictable and dynamic conditions. A special role is given to the development of tactical literacy, which allows assessing the situation, making optimal decisions, planning and coordinating actions in operational circumstances, as well as flexibly adapting to changes.

In modern conditions of socio-political and economic transformations in Ukraine, tactical and special training acquires strategic importance, since its results directly affect the effectiveness of performing official tasks, ensuring public safety and protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens. Prospects for further research include in-depth study of innovative training methods, development of psychological and communicative competencies, implementation of simulation and digital technologies, and development of practice-oriented models that will help increase the readiness of law enforcement officers to act in complex and non-standard situations.

References:

1. Kondratiuk, N. S., Bubnova, A. S., & Paranytsia, S. P. (2025). The essence of tactical-special training in law enforcement activities. *Analytical and Comparative Jurisprudence*, 2, 612. <http://journal-app.uzhnu.edu.ua/article/download/327559/317328>

2. Kalaur, S., & Denysovskyi, M. (2022). Professional competence of a police officer: Methodological and practical aspects of formation by means of training. *Pedagogical Sciences: Theory, History, Innovative Technologies*, 7–8, 71. http://dspace.tnpu.edu.ua/bitstream/123456789/27716/1/Kalaur_Denysovskyi.pdf
3. Shlomin, O. Yu. (2018). The content of professional competence of police officers. *Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Professional Education and Patriotic Education of the Personnel of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine* (pp. 266–268). Kharkiv. https://univd.edu.ua/general/publishing/konf/30_03_2018/pdf/86.pdf
4. Bilichenko, V., & Huba, N. (2025). Relevance of the issue of professional psychological training of police officers in modern conditions. Actual problems of service and combat activities of the security and defense sector of Ukraine: Proceedings of the All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference (p. 212). Dnipro State University of Internal Affairs. <https://er.dduvs.edu.ua/bitstream/123456789/16054/1/Збірник%20СБД%2025.04.2025%20макет.pdf#page=212>
5. Shlomin, O. Yu. (2017). Components of the professional competence of the future police officer. *Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Professional Education and Patriotic Education of the Personnel of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine* (p. 240). Kharkiv. https://univd.edu.ua/general/publishing/konf/07_04_2017/pdf/74.pdf
6. Hidenko, Ye. (2023). The role and place of tactical literacy in the performance of service and combat tasks in the organization of the security and defense sector of the state. *Criminal Law and Criminology. Criminal-Executive Law. Criminal Procedure and Criminalistics. Forensic Science. Operative-Search Activity. Judiciary. Prosecution and Advocacy. Current Issues of Jurisprudence*, 2, 183. <https://dspace.wunu.edu.ua/bitstream/316497/54902/1/Гіденко.PDF>
7. Karpenko, O. M., Korolov, A. V., & Chernolutskyi, D. V. (2025). Tactical-special training of police officers in the use of improvised means. *Ukrainian Police Science: Theory, Legislation, Practice*, 2, 85. <https://www.policystyka.dnuvs.ukr.education/index.php/policystyka/article/download/264/238>
8. Hidenko, Ye. S. (2024). General characteristics and levels of tactical literacy of the personnel of the units of the National Police of Ukraine involved in the performance of service and combat tasks. *Legal Scientific Electronic Journal*, 1. http://www.lsej.org.ua/1_2024/141.pdf